

Mapping breeding — challenging paradigms

An exercise to map a good story

Why would one give away his advantage over others? And still be successful? How spatial and situational awareness matter

The story of Aaron Avner, a farmer.

There was a farmer who grew excellent quality corn. Every year, he won the award for the best grown corn. (...)

The farmer, to grow his crop, for example corn, needs good seeds. Breeding by selection procedures, and/or crossing, helps, over time, produce “better” seeds for “better” crops. The “better” crops get rewarded.

All farmers in the area do this, that is represented by a system. As they are, in this case, competing for an award, they can be considered rivals.

So all farmers, with their own methods and knowledge, breed their corn. One get awarded, and the same goes on every year.

A very simplified representation of breeding for an award-winning corn

Evolution axis

The story of Aaron Avner, a farmer.

(...)

One year a newspaper reporter interviewed him and learned something interesting about how he grew it. The reporter discovered that the farmer shared his seed corn with his neighbors. "How can you afford to share your best seed corn with your neighbors when they are entering corn in competition with yours each year?" the reporter asked.

(...)

The reporter is surprised that the farmer would give away his advantage over the others. Why??

He assumes that one would have a close up strategy, keep his breeding methods and the result of it – his award-winning, best seeds, to himself. The reporter also assumes that the core of breeding is starting with a good seed. The third assumption is that everyone is working hard on their breeding process.

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“Why sir,” said the farmer, “Didn’t you know? The wind picks up pollen from the ripening corn and swirls it from field to field.

(...)

The many times awarded farmer reminds of a forgotten part of the process: pollination. While it is obvious to all farmers that corn needs pollination, they did not see it as an essential element, as they performed the wished crossings presumably by themselves during their breeding process. And the pollination to get a fruit was just taken as granted in their own field.

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“Why sir,” said the farmer, “Didn’t you know? The wind picks up pollen from the ripening corn and swirls it from field to field. If my neighbors grow inferior corn, cross-pollination will steadily degrade the quality of my corn. If I am to grow good corn, I must help my neighbors grow good corn.”

The farmer has not only a breeding pipeline (1) as his neighbors; he is aware of the whole system around his own field, and takes advantage of it, as an ecosystem. He opens (2) the result of his breeding to this ecosystem (3). He uses the existing cross pollination, to his own advantage. The result will be that he can start from good corn, with other good corn input (4) from his neighbor’s breeding from good corn. So he fully integrates pollination and cross pollination from the ecosystem in his breeding strategy (5).

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Indeed, if all farmers would think like the reporter assumes, they would focus on their breeding pipeline (1). However, they are actually in a whole system around their own fields, without taking it into account, the system works as an ecosystem (3), with or without their awareness. They close the result of their breeding (2), but still get cross pollination from others (3). If all start over with their best quality corn, including the “looser” of the competition, the existing cross pollination might reduce the quality of the own corn (4). Failing to see cross pollination from the ecosystem in their breeding strategy (5) would eventually reduce the corn quality.

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Spreading "good" (seeds, or other) can be a successful strategy to improve existing, already on-going steps towards "the better", given good understanding of underlying processes. Another advantage is, the own need of resources is reduced, as the functioning ecosystem provides its own dynamic and (shared) resources, eliminating duplicates, thus accelerating the movement. Citizen science, global collaboration across places and fields of interests, open source or creative common resources are such ways of functioning.

It does not matter if this farmer actually exists. What does matter is to understand that sharing is not necessarily a disadvantage, that spatial and situational awareness are very important, and that collaboration – whether international or not – can accelerate a movement.

And what the story also shows : ecosystem dynamics affect you, whether you acknowledge it or not. So maybe using them for the "best" could be a promising way to walk....

